

SOME BIOECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ZAMIOKULKAS PLANT AND METHODS OF REPRODUCTION.

Tadjibaeva Lolakhxon Akbarali qizi

Fergana State University, teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8282786>

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются виды, полезные свойства, посадка и способы размножения в домашних условиях Замиокулькаса, как суккулентное растение, которое центр происхождения является тропические районы.

Ключевые слова: Замиокулькас, суккулент, экзотические растения, вегетативные органы, интродуценты, токсическое вещество, рахис, интерьер.

Annotation. The article discusses the types, useful properties, planting and methods of reproduction at home of Zamioculcas, as a succulent plant, which the center of origin is tropical areas.

Keywords: Zamioculcas, succulent, exotic plants, vegetative organs, introducers, toxic substance, rachis, interior.

Currently, in many countries of the world, you can find flowering plants, ornamental vines or a variety of introduced plants growing in tropical and subtropical regions. The variety, appearance, and characteristics of these plants also differ.

As one of such introduced plants in our country, the Zamioculcas plant is popular and is grown mainly, because of its beautiful leaves.

Рис 1.

Zamioculcas - (lat. zamioculcas) is a representative of the Araceae family, whose origin is tropical Africa. This plant got its name because of the appearance of its leaves.

Features.

Zamioculcas is a tuberous herbaceous plant with a shortened stem. The petals of this flower are dark green, with a complex web-like structure reaching up to 1 meter in length. The flowers are not decorative (Fig.1).

Until the end of the XX century, this plant was almost not used as an ornamental plant. In 1996, as a result of sales at public Dutch flower auctions, the flower began to attract the attention of amateurs and professionals. Zamioculcas was first introduced in August 2007 in the form of compact, with smaller leaves growing up to 60 cm in length. Sometimes this flower is also called a dollar flower.

The Zamioculcas plant does not require excessive care, tolerates drought well, can grow even in conditions of low humidity, insufficient lighting. But for normal development, it is important to have a light that is protected from direct sunlight.

Useful properties.

Zamioculcas is considered a natural filter. Therefore, it is recommended to place it not only in homes, but also in hospitals, offices, especially small buildings where there are a lot of people. It can be placed in any room of the house, and placing it in the bedroom will make sleep healthier and stronger.

Increases the efficiency and activity of employees in offices and organizations. The reason is that a decrease in carbon dioxide in the air, an increase in oxygen levels, affects the brain, increasing attention. Having also the property of humidifying the air, this flower is recommended for patients with respiratory diseases.

Toxic properties.

For people:

1. The juice of this plant contains a substance that affects the skin and mucous membranes of the stem, leaves, even tubers. Itching, redness in contact with the skin or mucous membranes of the eyes can even cause burns.

2. It is also necessary to avoid ingestion of this substance. When children get into the stomach, they cause symptoms of poisoning: diarrhea, flatulence, an increase in body temperature, which can even lead to seizures.

3. For people suffering from allergies, dust in zamiokulkas can negatively affect their health. Most often, this situation occurs with prolonged contact with zamiokulkas.

For pets.

Getting even a small portion of Zamioculcas into the pet's stomach causes them severe poisoning and diarrhea. Untimely assistance leads to death.

It is worth noting that Zamioculcas itself is harmless and does not cause diarrhea or allergic reactions when it gets on leaves, flowers or other parts. Growing this flower at home will not lead to deterioration of health.

Methods of reproduction.

It is desirable to propagate Zamioculcas during the period of intensive vegetation-in late spring-early summer. Reproduction of this plant takes longer. The formation of peanut leaves from tubers also requires a period of 3-4 months.

Table 1.

Reproduction by cuttings.

Name of the plant	Age of plant	Sample	Length of the sample	Time	Time spent on rooting	Period	The first leaves
Zamioculcas	3-4 years	leaves	7-15 sm	19 th of december	20 th of february	6-9 week	May-July

Reproduction by cuttings.

Reproduction in this way is convenient, and this method is mainly used in floriculture.

In the experiment, the perennial leaves of zamioculcas were selected and cut off with a length of 7-15 cm. Water was used as a substrate for rooting. It is worth noting that soil can also be used as a substrate. On December 19, the sample was placed in room temperature water (boiled, settled), 2 tablets of activated carbon were thrown into the water so that the sample would not rot. The first roots were observed on February 20.

You can propagate zamioculcas vegetatively at any time of the year. But breeding in the winter months may not give the expected effect or take a long time.

Zamioculcas are also propagated by strips of leaves or by separate pruning of leaf plates with short strips. But it takes 6-9 months to achieve the expected result.

Reproduction by means of corms. The most popular and easiest way is to transplant several tubers of a large zamiokulkas to a separate peduncle.

Propagation by seeds. This method is often used by breeders and experienced growers. Because zamiokulkas practically does not bloom in indoor conditions, it is difficult to get seeds and grow them.

In summary zamioculcas stands out among ornamental plants in that it does not need excessive care, reproduces easily, and also has a beautiful appearance. It will fit into the interior of any room, organization or office. Since the cultivation of this plant has a positive effect on human health, it can be recommended to grow it anywhere: both in apartments and in institutions.

References:

1. <https://na-zemle.info/komnatnye-rasteniya/kaktusy-i-sukkulenty>
2. Д. Князева, Т. Князева, Комнатные растения. — М.: ЭКСМО, 2014. — С. 162.
3. Чуб В. Загадки ароидных // Цветоводство. — 2008. — № 3. — С. 58—61.
4. ru.wikipedia.org
5. Tadjibayeva, L., & Xoldoraliev, S. (2023). Popular indoor plants recommended for use in preschools and their characteristics. *Journal of Advanced Scientific Research* (82-85).
6. Tadjibayeva, L., Xoldoraliev, S., Maxmudova, K., & Qurolova, F. (2023). TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA EKOLOGIK MADANIYATNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MADANIY O'SIMLIK LARNING O'RNI. *Наука и инновация*, 1(5), 71-74.
7. Xoldoraliev, S. (2023). INDOOR PLANTS THAT CANNOT BE USED IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS. *Наука и инновация*, 1(11), 182-184.

8. Tadjibayeva, L. A. Q. (2022). DRACAENA MARGINATA AYRIM BIOEKOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI VA KO'PAYTIRISH USULI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 716-719.
9. Tadjibayeva, L. (2023). BENJAMIN FIKUSI (FICUS BENJAMINA) O 'SIMLIGINING AYRIM BIOEKOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI VA UNI YETISHTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. *Наука и инновация*, 1(4), 199-202.
10. Qizi, T. L. A. (2023). *Bazella rubra*. Useful properties and cultivation technology. *JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURE & HORTICULTURE*, 3(4), 109-112.
11. Tadjibayeva, L., Xoldoralieva, S., Maxmudova, K., & Qurolova, F. (2023). SHAHAR SANOAT ZONALARINI KO'KALAMZORLASHTIRISHDA TERAQ (POPULUS L.) O'SIMLIGINING AHAMIYATI. *Наука и инновация*, 1(6), 16-18.
12. Tadjibayeva, L. (2023). SHAHAR HUDUDLARIDA ATROF-MUHIT IFLOSLANISHINING AHOLI SALOMATLIGIGA SALBIY TA'SIRI. *Наука и инновация*, 1(5), 67-70.

